

Linking Research & Innovation for Gender Equality

D3.1 GEPs implementation during phase I

WP3 – Implementation of GEPs

Version: 1.00

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Executive Summary

This deliverable is the main deliverable of T3.2 *GEPs Implementation in Each RPO/ RFO - 1st Iteration of WP3 Implementation of GEPs*. The purpose of this report is to give an overview of the GEPs implementation activities conducted by RPOs/RFOs in the first iteration, period M18 – M30.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full form
GEPs	Gender Equality Plans
RPOs	Research Performing Organisations
RFOs	Research Funding Organisations
UZG	University of Zagreb - Faculty of Electrical and Computer Engineering
STU BA	Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava
ULB	Université Libre de Bruxelles
ECE NTUA	School of Electrical & Computer Engineering - National Technical University of Athens

IRB	Institute for Research in Biomedicine in Barcelona
YU	Yasar University
UNILE	Salento University
SRNSFG	Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia
UEFISCDI	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development & Innovation Funding in Romania
CU	Cardiff University

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose, scope, structure of the deliverable

CALIPER project supports 7 RPOs and 2 RFO in the development, implementation, and sustainability of their tailored gender equality plans (GEPs). Overall, WP3 *Implementation of GEPs* aims to support the implementation of the GEPs developed in the previous WP2 *Design and Development of Customised GEPs (CALIPER GEPs)*. GEPs are implemented in two iterative implementation phases to achieve institutional change for gender equality as defined by each RPO/ RFO in T2.3 *GEPs Design and Development*. After the end of each iteration phase, the results are analysed through Key Performance Indicators leading to the redesign and refinement of the GEP. The present deliverable aims at reporting the GEPs activities implemented during phase 1 at each CALIPER RPO/RFO referring to the respective timelines and including a statistical overview of the implemented GEP activities during this phase which lasted from June 2021 to June 2022 (M18 –M30).

The leader of the WP3 is UZG, and the following partners are the GEP implementing partners of the CALIPER project:

- RPOs: IRB, ECE NTUA, STU BA, ULB, UNILE, UZG, YU;
- RFOs: UEFISCDI, SRNSFG.

The structure of the deliverable is the following. In the second chapter we give an overview of the GEPs implementation process. In the third chapter we give an overview of actions implemented by the consortium, focusing on the timeline, involved staff and collaboration with the CALIPER R&I Hub. In the fourth chapter we briefly present GEPs' implemented actions for each RPO/RFO.

1.2 Relation to other WPs & Tasks

This deliverable is the main deliverable of T3.2 *GEPs Implementation in Each RPO/ RFO - 1st Iteration* of WP3 *Implementation of GEPs*. The reported actions are planned in the RPOs/RFOs GEPs as designed in the previous work WP2 *Design and Development of Customised GEPs*. WP3 is strictly connected with WP4 *Monitoring and Evaluation*, since monitoring and evaluation activities are based on the actions implemented within WP3. This report D3.1 is complementary to the deliverable of WP4 *Monitoring and Evaluation D4.2 Interim Formative Evaluation Report – phase 1* in the sense that it covers both partially implemented and completely finalized GEP actions, while D4.2 reports on implemented actions that have been completely finalized and evaluated. During the first iteration phase, in the frame of T3.1 *CALIPER HelpDesk and GEPs Implementation* a CALIPER Help Desk has been set up to support partner RPOs and RFOs in a customized way throughout the whole implementation process. This deliverable also contains a brief overview of the CALIPER Help Desk activities. In addition, this report contains a brief overview of activities within Task 3.4 *Redesign and Refinement of GEPs*, which followed T3.2. Task T3.2, reported in this deliverable, anticipates T3.3 *GEPs Implementation in Each RPO/ RFO - 2nd Iteration*. The GEPs implementation process has been supported by activities within WP5 *Engagement, Change Management and Sustainability* and WP6 *Dissemination and Communication*.

2 Overview of the GEPs implementation process

The first implementation phase of GEPs covers the period of M18 - M30 (June 2021 – June 2022). This task was coordinated by UZG with the active involvement of all partners.

During this period, 7 RPOs (IRB, ECE NTUA, STU BA, ULB, UNILE, UZG, YU) and 2 RFOs (UEFISCDI, SRNSFG) put into practice part of the measures foreseen in their tailored GEPs developed within the scope of WP2. Actions were designed in alignment with D4.1 *Evaluation Methodology* so that the same logical framework of Goals and Objectives, Output/Outcomes/Impact Indicators guided the design, implementation, and evaluation of each action in the GEPs. GEPs actions were specifically tailored by partners to address each specific institutional context and to cover a wide array of areas of intervention: human resources, institutional governance, institutional communication, research/research funding, transfer to market, student services, teaching, and sexual harassment/gender-based violence. In addition, two crosscutting strategic areas were addressed: intersectionality and collaborative actions¹.

Responsible for the implementation process were the GEP Working Groups set up in each participating RPO/RFO and supported by the specific strategy elaborated in T5.1 for *Internal Engagement and Change Management*. UZG prepared timelines for each partner and kept track of correct and on time implementation. It is important to emphasise that not all actions that started the implementation were also finalized in the 1st implementation phase. Some actions were partially implemented, and their implementation will continue in the 2nd implementation phase. This deliverable reports on all implemented actions, including both the actions that have been partially implemented and those that have been completely finalized in the 1st implementation phase. After the finalization of the implementation of an action, a formative self-evaluation of the action was performed by the responsible partner. The evaluations were performed within WP4 and are reported in the report D4.2 *Interim Formative Evaluation Report – Phase 1*.

A mutual learning session was organized in M30 as part of an official project meeting to reflectively share and exchange experiences and overcome obstacles in view of the 2nd iteration. In addition, a follow up mutual learning session took place in M33 within the monthly online consortium meeting.

The following sections of this chapter report on the work carried out within the 1st implementation phase in WP3 to facilitate the implementation of GEPs in partner organisations:

- Monitoring the implementation of GEPs (T3.2),
- Supporting the implementation of GEPs via CALIPER HelpDesk (T3.1),
- Preparing for the 2nd implementation phase via redesign and refinement of GEP actions (T3.4).

2.1 The process of monitoring the implementation of GEPs

Within task T3.2, monitoring and reporting tools were developed to keep track of the progress of the GEP's implementation in RPOs/RFOs. The monitoring process was three-fold: **continuous, monthly, and quarterly**.

Continuous monitoring was performed via a joint shared dynamical Gantt chart in Teamwork, in view of overseeing timely implementation of actions. Partners were given instructions during monthly online consortium meetings about how to include their actions and timeframes in Teamwork. The data collected in Teamwork included title, start, end, area, responsible staff, and description of the action. The progress was regularly updated on the Gantt chart, and this provided a transparent and easy way to oversee the timely

¹ See D1.1 and D4.2 for a description of the different areas of intervention and cross-cutting areas.

implementation of actions. Below screen shots of the Gantt chart in Teamwork are reported. Further screen shots of the Gantt chart with all actions reported are available in Annex A.

Figure 1 Teamwork section for partner UZG

Figure 2 Gantt chart in Teamwork for IRB

Monthly monitoring was conducted during regular online consortium meetings. In each meeting, every partner reported on the ongoing activities, completed actions and other relevant information.

Table 1 Online consortium meetings in the period M18 - M30

ID of the meeting	Date of the meeting
14	14 September 2021
15	12 October 2021
16	9 November 2021
17	14 December 2021
18	8 February 2021
19	8 March 2021
20	12 April 2021
21	10 May 2021

Quarterly monitoring was reported in M22, M26 and M30 through written reports. A dedicated [monitoring tool](#) was developed and shared with partners. The aim of the monitoring tool, jointly developed by SV (as

WP4 leader) and UZG (as WP3 leader) was to collect data need for both WP3 and WP4, in order to facilitate partners' work.

Planned	Activities			Actors			Output			Outcome indicators					
	M22	M26	M30	M22	M26	M30	M22	M26	M30	Short term			Medium-term		
										M22	M26	M30	Planned		M30
	Title of the action: Setting up a mentoring program														
	Brief description of the action (if the title is not self-explanatory):														
	Area/topic: Institutional governance														
	Type of action (soft/structural): Soft														
	Is it a collaborative action? (yes/no) No														
	Does the action implementation involve both iterations? (yes/no) yes														
	Does the action change internal procedures? (yes/no) no														
	Does the action impact directly or prepare the ground for suggesting future changes in strategic documents of your institution? no														
1	Establish mentoring guidelines and documents						Published training materials and didactic units for mentors and mentees			Increased awareness about the benefits, opportunities and challenges regarding mentoring program.					
2	Recruitment / matching of mentors and mentees						Number of mentors recruited; number of mentees seeking support.			Matched mentor – mentee pairs.					
3	Hold training seminars for mentors; mentees						Number of training seminars held; number of participants (gender)			Awareness of responsibilities and duties; challenges of mentoring relations. Adjusted expectations				Experienced mentors; mentor-to-mentor support network; expansion of professional networks.	
4	Mentor and mentee meetings						Number of mentor – mentee meetings held			Increased confidence, well-being, job satisfaction; improved understanding of career advancement requisites, etc.				Improved networking and career prospects for mentees, etc.	

Figure 3 Tool for quarterly monitoring for WP3 and WP4

2.2 Bilateral calls and CALIPER HelpDesk

During the first iteration phase, in the frame of T3.1 a CALIPER Help Desk has been set up to support RPO and RFO partners in a customized way throughout the implementation process. A mix of activities were carried out: in particular, regular bilateral calls and thematic help desk sessions.

3 rounds of bilateral calls were organized during the 1st implementation iteration (in October 2021, in March 2022 and in May 2022). Within each round, 9 parallel calls were organized by SV with representatives of the WGs. Before each round, partners were invited to send to SV a list of topics/issues they wanted to discuss, in order for SV to prepare and provide related expert guidance and support. Depending on the specific needs of the partners, SV also searched for useful resources, studies, tools, and good practices which were then added to the repository of resources elaborated within T2.3. VIL and UZG participated in the bilateral calls as respectively project coordinator and WP3 leader.

In addition, 6 thematic online Help Desk sessions were organized during the first iteration. The sessions were open to the whole consortium and at least 2 people per partner were invited to take part. The topics to be addressed during the Help Desk sessions were identified directly by the partners at the beginning of the first iteration. The 6 thematic Help Desk sessions addressed the following topics/issues: the organization of the WIN event (providing inputs for different themes and formats), engaging internal stakeholders, how to deal with resistances (the session took the form of a training organized in collaboration with the SUPERA project), gender sensitive institutional communication (in collaboration with the SUPERA project), presentation and discussion of the Gearing Roles' mentoring programme FELISE (in collaboration with the Gearing Roles project); how to involve men in gender equality work (this session was organized in collaboration with ULB in the frame of T5.1 and with a an invited speaker from the Gender-SMART project). In general, Help Desk sessions lasted between 1 and 2 hours, except for the training on how to deal with resistances which lasted 4 hours and a half, divided in three shorter modules. Partners participated in all Help Desk sessions.

2.3 Mutual learning session

A mutual learning session was organised in M30 to reflect and share experiences and overcome obstacles in view of the 2nd iteration. It took place during the 6th Project Management Team Hybrid Meeting, June 22-23, 2022, in Woburn House, London, UK. Representatives of all partners were present, as well as members of

the Advisory Board. WP3 leader gave an overview of the efforts executed by the partners in WP3. RPOs/RFOs presented their progress based on their GEP thematic areas: human resources, institutional governance, institutional communication, research funding and teaching, transfer to market, collaborative actions, student services, intersectionality and sexual harassment. The main points of discussion were overall lessons learnt in action implementation (positive/negative key take aways, resistances, etc.), possible refinement of the action and the sustainability of it, and R&I Hubs engagement.

Day I: 22 June 2022			Day II: 23 June 2022		
Time (British Summer Time)	Item	Partner	Time (British Summer Time)	Item	Partner
9:15 - 9:30	Arrival – Coffee – Get Together	all	9:15 - 9:30	Arrival	
9:30 - 9:45	Welcome and agenda Professor Ole H Petersen Kyriaki Karydou	CU VIL	9:30 - 9:35	Welcome - Agenda	VIL
9:45 - 10:05	WP7 - Project Management	VIL	9:35 - 10:00	WP4 Monitoring and evaluation T4.2 Internal formative evaluation	SV
10:05 - 11:30	WP3 - Implementation of GEPs Partner present their GEP implemented actions during first iteration phase	All RPOs/RFOs, Moderated by UZG FER & SV	10:00-10:10	WP5 – Engagement, change management and sustainability Task 5.1 Internal engagement and change management strategy	ULB
11:30 - 11:45	Coffee break		10:10 - 10:30	WP5 – Engagement, change management and sustainability Task 5.2 Summary of <i>win</i> events Task 5.3 Raising awareness and engagement activities	VIL
11:45 - 13:15	WP3 - Implementation of GEPs (Continuation)	All RPOs/RFOs, Moderated by UZG FER & SV	10:30 - 10:50	WP5 – Engagement, change management and sustainability Task 5.4 Sustaining and replicating in STEM	VIL, all
13:15 - 14:15	Lunch break		10:50 - 11:05	Coffee break	
14:15 - 15:30	WP3 - Implementation of GEPs (Continuation)	All RPOs/RFOs, Moderated by UZG FER & SV	11:05 - 11:30	WP6 - Dissemination and Communication Task 6.1 Dissemination plan and channels	VIL
15:30 - 15:40	Coffee break		11:30 - 12:00	WP6 - Dissemination and Communication Task 6.3 External communication and multiplying effect	CU
15:40 - 16:30	WP3 - Implementation of GEPs (Continuation)	All RPOs/RFOs, Moderated by UZG FER & SV	12:00 - 12:20	WP6 - Dissemination and Communication Task 6.4 Development of policy briefings and final conference	VIL
16:30 - 17:00	WP3 GEPs refinement and re-design: towards institutionalising change (T3.4)	IRB	12:20 - 13:00	Open discussion - Q&A	All
17:00	End of day 1		13:00 - 14:00	Lunch	
20.00	Dinner		14:00	End of Day 2	
			Right after end of Day 2	Social activity: Visiting the British Museum's new exhibition on Feminine Power	

Figure 4 Agenda for the 6th Project Management Team Hybrid Meeting

Members of Advisory Board participated and gave talks:

- Sophie Ivarsson: *Sex & Gender dimension in research and innovation*
- Britt-Marie Söderberg Torstensson: *WRC s – the most effective sources for engaging women in gender equal sustainable national, regional and local development*

<p>Theme: Sex & Gender dimension in research and innovation SUMMARY FROM FORGEN MEMBERS</p> <p>FORGEN Fostering Opportunities for Europe</p>	<p>Winnet Sweden, Women in Network</p> <p>WRC s – the most effective sources for engaging women in gender equal sustainable national, regional and local development</p> <p>The Swedish National Federation of Women Resource Centers, WRC, Transfer to Market 22 June 2022 at CALIPER Meeting</p> <p>Britt-Marie Söderberg Torstensson, President, Winnet Sweden, Europe</p>
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Figure 5 Front pages of presentations by the members of the Advisory board at the 6th Project Management Team Hybrid Meeting

Figure 6 Participants of the 6th Project Management Team Hybrid Meeting

In addition, a follow up mutual learning session took place within the 24th Online Consortium Meeting on September 13th, 2022 (M33). All partners participated. The focus was on the reflection of the overall GEPs implementation process: lessons learnt from the 1st implementation phase on overcoming resistances, avoiding delays, and engaging stakeholders in view of the 2nd implementation phase.

2.4 Redesign and refinement of GEPs

Task T3.4 *Redesign and Refinement of GEPs* is aimed at collecting all the information and data related to the GEP's actions that, on the basis of the results of the first implementation phase and formative evaluation, need to be re-designed or refined.

Dedicated guidelines were provided to partners by IRB as T3.4 leader in order to report refined/redesigned actions as well as new or cancelled ones.

In D3.2 *Mini Reports on the Redesign and Refinement Elements in Each RPO/RFO* the new versions of the GEPs will be also included. It is important to mention that within the analysis carried out in the frame of the present document, as well as within T4.2 about the interim formative evaluation, some misalignments emerged as concerns the way partners have classified actions (among the 8 areas of interventions²) and the two cross-cutting areas (intersectionality and collaborative actions). Moreover, different interpretations were adopted also regarding the classification between soft and structural actions. As a consequence, the need to adjust the mentioned misalignments in the frame of the development of the new versions of the GEPs emerged. Therefore, tailored instructions will be provided to partners for the elaboration of the new versions to ensure GEPs will be more harmonized, in terms of the classifications of actions as mentioned above. All GEPs' actions will be classified among the 8 areas of interventions while "collaborative actions" and "intersectionality" will be considered as cross-cutting features/labels to be attributed to each one of the actions measure whereas relevant.

² Institutional governance, human resources management, research/research funding, teaching, students services, transfer to market, institutional communication, sexual harassment/gender based violence (see D1.1 and D4.2 for areas' explanations).

3 Overview of implemented actions/measures

In this chapter we give a report on all implemented actions by RPOs/RFOs in the 1st implementation phase. It is important to emphasise that in this report with “implemented actions” we mean both the actions that have been partially implemented and those that have been completely finalized in the 1st implementation phase. Here the focus is on the following aspects:

- overall data on the number of actions implemented,
- timeline of the implemented actions,
- internal actors and external stakeholders engaged in implementation of actions.

As for the achievement of goals and objectives, output / outcomes / impact indicators of implemented actions, a formative evaluation was conducted within the framework of *WP4 Monitoring and Evaluation* only for those actions that have been completely finalized in the 1st implementation phase. The results are reported in deliverable *D4.2 Interim Formative Evaluation Report – phase 1*.

It is important to mention that the results of this report differ from the ones of *D4.2 Interim Formative Evaluation Report – phase 1*. Indeed, while *D4.2* considers only finalized and evaluated actions in its analysis, the present document includes also partially implemented actions.

3.1 Data collection process

The data for this report were collected from three sources.

Firstly, data were collected through the shared data collection tool already mentioned in the section 2.1 and set up for both WP3 and WP4. It enabled quarterly monitoring of the progress of the GEPs’ implementation, in M22, M26 and M30. In such tool, partners provided information on the name, description, area, and type of action. Furthermore, partners reported on the activities conducted, actors involved, output and outcome indicators.

In addition, data were collected from the *Monitoring and Evaluation Reports* produced by each RPO/RFO in M30/M31 within the framework of the *WP4 Monitoring and Evaluation*. The reports contain formative self-evaluation of each implemented action that was finalized in the 1st implementation phase. An extensive analysis of the results of the reports is provided in *D4.2 Interim Formative Evaluation Report – phase 1*. The following information about finalized actions were taken from the *Monitoring and Evaluation Reports* produced by each RPO/RFO: timeline, status of the action.

Finally, as last step, an [additional tool for data integration](#) was created in order to facilitate consistent integration of data collected from various sources over longer period of time and also collect some additional data (see below, Figure 7). It is important to clarify that despite WP3 and WP4 leaders have jointly set up common tools for partners to report data under both WP3 and WP4 (e.g., the monitoring spreadsheet, *Monitoring and Evaluation Report*), in order to reduce partners’ efforts in the reporting phase, for the purpose of the present analysis, additional data were found to be necessary. Therefore, UZG as WP3 leader shared with partners an additional tool to collect more detailed info about internal and external stakeholders. In a few cases, some misalignments appear between what included by RPOs/RFOs in their *Monitoring and Evaluation Reports* (WP4) and what they reported in the data integration tool (WP3). This explains why results of the present document slightly differ from the ones of *D4.2*. Those discrepancies are described for each partner in their respective sections of this report.

Indeed, in M33 each RPO/RFO conducted a revision and integration of the data about all implemented actions, delays and stakeholders involved, in order to provide up to date complete picture of the implemented actions, both finalized and partially implemented.

1		
2		
3		
4	Action title (same as in the GEP)	
5	Area	
6	Soft/structural	
7	Implemented (yes/no/partially)	
8	Iteration (yes/no)	
9	Actual starting date of implementation (in GEP)	
10	Actual ending date of implementation (in GEP)	
11	Planned starting month of implementation	
12	Planned ending month of implementation	
13	Short explanation for delay	
14	Collaborative action? (yes/no)	
15	Type of external stakeholder	
16	INSTRUCTIONS: Here we count persons and institutions in separate rows	
17	Academic and research institutions (count all persons even if they belong to the same institution)	? F / ? M
18	Academic and research institutions (count all institutions)	
19	Public sector (excluding academia/public research institutions) (count all persons)	? F / ? M
20	Public sector (excluding academia/public research institutions) (count institutions)	
21	Policy makers (count all persons)	? F / ? M
22	Policy makers (count institutions)	
23	Industry (count all persons)	? F / ? M
24	Industry (count institutions)	
25	persons	? F / ? M
26	institutions	
27	Feminist NGOs / gender experts (count all persons)	? F / ? M
28	Feminist NGOs / gender experts (count institutions)	
29	Type of internal stakeholder (number of individuals F and M)	
30	INSTRUCTIONS: The same individual can belong to different categories (ex. Human Resources Manager belongs to Management, Administration and CALIPER working group so it should be counted in all three categories)	
31	CALIPER working group	? F / ? M
32	Research	
33	Young researchers (no PhD)	? F / ? M
34	Researchers (with PhD, not permanent)	? F / ? M
35	Project managers	? F / ? M
36	Other	? F / ? M
37	Academia	
38	Students	? F / ? M
39	Professors	? F / ? M
40	Equality and diversity committee (or similar (Gender) Equality/the Diversity bodies)	? F / ? M
41	Other	? F / ? M
42	Management	
43	Rector	? F / ? M
44	Vice rector	? F / ? M
45	Dean	? F / ? M
46	Vice dean	? F / ? M
47	Head of Department	? F / ? M
48	Head of Office	? F / ? M
49	Other	? F / ? M
50	Administration	
51	Secretary office	? F / ? M
52	Public Relations / Communications office	? F / ? M
53	Research / Project Support Office	? F / ? M
54	Rectorate	? F / ? M
55	Human Resources Office	? F / ? M
56	Legal Office	? F / ? M
57	Diversity and Equality committee (or similar (Gender) Equality/the Diversity bodies)	? F / ? M
58	Student Services Office	? F / ? M
59	Technical support	? F / ? M
60	Educational Support Office	? F / ? M
61	Library	? F / ? M

Figure 7 Tool for the revision and data integration

3.2 Implemented actions in numbers

As already mentioned above, while D4.2 *Interim Formative Evaluation Report – phase 1* report only finalized and evaluated actions, the present deliverable reports on both partially implemented actions and finalized ones, referring to both two groups of actions as implemented actions.

During the 1st implementation period, the 7 RPOs and 2 RFOs implemented 90 actions in total. Most of the actions, 58 of them (64%), were finalized. For those actions partners performed extensive self-evaluation of each finalized action under the scope of WP4 and this is reported in detail in D4.2 *Interim Formative Evaluation Report – phase 1*. The remaining 32 (36%) have been partially implemented.

Figure 8 Distribution of implemented actions

The distribution of the implemented actions per partner is the following:

- IRB: 6 finalized actions
- ECE NTUA: 7 finalized actions
- SRNSFG: 16 finalized and 6 partially implemented actions
- STU BA: 2 finalized and 4 partially implemented actions
- UEFISCDI: 3 finalized and 3 partially implemented actions
- ULB: 5 finalized and 11 partially implemented actions
- UNILE: 7 finalized actions
- UZG: 6 finalized actions
- YU: 6 finalized and 8 partially implemented actions.

Figure 9 Distribution of implemented actions per partner

The implemented actions cover a wide array of areas: human resources, institutional governance, institutional communication, research/research funding, transfer to market, student services, teaching and sexual harassment/gender-based violence. In addition, two crosscutting strategic areas were addressed: intersectionality and collaborative actions³.

The distribution of all implemented actions per area is the following: collaborative actions (16), institutional governance (15), institutional communication (13), human resources (11), research / research funding (10), teaching (8), sexual harassment (8), student services (5), transfer to market (2) and intersectionality (2).

³ See D1.1 and D4.2 for a description of the different areas of intervention and cross-cutting areas.

Figure 10 Distribution of actions per area

The top three areas according to the number of the implemented actions are:

- collaborative action (18%)
- institutional governance (17%)
- institutional communication (14%).

They represent the 49% of implemented actions. This does not surprise since partner institutions are in the first year of GEPs implementation. Therefore, their priorities are to adapt governance mechanisms to enable GEP implementation and set up gender equality bodies (area of institutional governance), promote internally and externally the implementation of GEPs, as well as gain support from stakeholders (institutional communication and collaborative actions).

Figure 11 Share of actions per area

The actions were divided in two categories, “soft” and “structural”. In view of this deliverable, with soft measures we mean those measures which do not impact on the structure of the organization itself (yet), and are usually shorter-term, preparatory measures, aimed at building preconditions for institutional change. On

the contrary, structural measures are those actions/provisions that change the institutional structure, rules and procedures of the organization and are therefore medium-long term and even permanent measures.

Larger part of actions has been classified as 'soft' (59 actions or 66%), and the remaining ones as 'structural' (31 actions or 34%).

Figure 12 Distribution of actions on soft and structural

When looking at how structural actions are distributed across the areas, they are the most present in the following areas which make 77% of implemented structural actions:

- institutional governance (12),
- human resources (4),
- sexual harassment (4),
- institutional communication (4).

The result is not unexpected as several RPOs/RFOs set up GE bodies/machineries (institutional governance) and support measures for researchers (human resources) that are going to stay after project completion. Also, actions within the sexual harassment area are present as most of the partners are implementing protocols/codes of conduct that were not existing before and are embedded as new procedures, often under the responsibility of the above-mentioned GE bodies/machineries.

When looking at how soft actions are distributed across the areas, they are the most present in the following areas which make 42% of implemented soft actions:

- collaborative actions (16),
- institutional communication (9).

Figure 13 Distribution of soft and structural actions across areas

The soft actions implemented in these areas are mostly related to setting up institutional websites designated to gender equality and organizing WIN events in collaboration with R&I Hubs, as planned in the CALIPER project.

The following figure shows the status of structural actions across areas (finalized or partly implemented). We can observe that almost 70% of all structural actions that have been initiated, was also finalized already in the 1st implementation phase, and therefore evaluated and reported in detail in D4.2 *Interim Formative Evaluation Report – phase 1*.

Figure 14 Status of structural actions

When looking at how structural measures are distributed across partners, we see that in the 1st implementation phase of the GEP all partners favoured soft measures over structural. The share of structural measures ranges from 17% (UZG, IRB, UEFISCDI) to SRNSFG (45%). The remaining partners fall in between: UNILE (29%), STU BA (33%), YU (36%), ULB (38%), ECE NTUA (43%).

Figure 15 Distribution of soft and structural actions across partners

3.3 Collaboration with CALIPER R&I Hubs

CALIPER R&I Hubs with representatives from the local innovation ecosystems have been established during task T2.2 (one Hub per partner). The description of the external stakeholders that are part of each Hub is presented in D2.2 *Reporting results of multi-stakeholder dialogues*. The external stakeholders of the CALIPER R&I Hub belong to four sectors: academia, industry, civil society, and public sector. The partners have reported that a total of 139 external stakeholders have been engaged in their local R&I Hubs.

In this section we give an overview of collaboration with external stakeholders in the implementation of the GEP actions within the 1st implementation phase. Data shows that all RPOs/RFOs engaged in collaboration with external stakeholders while implementing GEPs in the 1st implementation phase.

The graph below shows how beyond the 16 actions classified as “collaborative” as such” (6 of those being WIN events), a collaborative feature implying the engagement of external stakeholders was embedded across actions from different areas. Overall, partners collaborated with external stakeholders in the implementation of 35 actions (9 of which were WIN events). It is worth mentioning how two out of the 35 actions have a structural impact on the institution while the remaining ones are considered as soft measures. Also, to be noted that all WIN events had a collaborative feature.

Figure 16 Distribution of collaborative and non-collaborative actions

In the following table we give the number of actions where external stakeholders participated. It is worth mentioning that in most cases the actions involved more than one type of stakeholder, and often single stakeholder participated in multiple actions. More detail about each action is available in the following chapter *Implemented actions per partner*.

The most involved category of external stakeholders in the implementation of actions were other RPOs and RFOs. Academic and research institutions participated in the 77% of collaborative actions (27 out of 35). Most of these actions were implemented by RFOs, SRNSFG and UEFISCDI. For example, SRNSFG collaborated in actions aiming at establishing more gender sensitive research projects evaluation process, while UEFISCDI implemented actions focusing on more gender sensitive internal procedures. Indeed, RFOs have, by definition, closer relations with external stakeholders (and typically RPOs) in their role of evaluating and funding research projects. Still, RPOs established collaborations with other academic partners in most cases to share experience and knowledge on GEP's implementation.

The second most engaged category were industry players, that were involved in 48% of the actions (17 out of 35). These actions were evenly distributed among partners: 8 out of 9 RPOs/RFOs involved industry players in at least one action. The actions they participated mostly were WIN events, and actions providing female role models from the industry.

Stakeholders belonging to the category of public sector (other than academic and research institutions) participated in 22% of actions (8 out of 35), also in this case, WIN event mostly.

Feminist NGOs / gender experts were involved in 25% of the actions (9 out of 35) and other civil society organisations in 28% of the actions (10 out of 35). These two categories of stakeholders were mostly involved in the same actions, almost all implemented by the RFOs, UEFISCDI and SRNSFG. For example, SRNSFG collaborated in actions aiming at establishing more gender sensitive research projects evaluation process.

The least involved category were the policy makers, taking part in 3 soft actions.

Table 2 Distribution of actions involving stakeholders

	Number of actions involving academic and research institutions	Number of actions involving public sector (excluding academia/public research institutions)	Number of actions involving policy makers	Number of actions involving industry players	Number of actions involving civil society (excluding feminist NGOs)	Number of actions involving feminist NGOs / gender experts
Human resources	2			1		
Institutional communication	3	1	1	1	1	
Institutional governance					1	
Student's services				2		
Research / Research funding	6	2		3	3	3
Teaching	1			1		
Transfer to market	1	1		1		
Sexual harassment	1					1
Collaborative actions	13	4	2	8	5	5

3.4 Participation of internal stakeholders in the implementation

In this section we give an overview of different internal stakeholders/actors who participated in the implementation process in RPOs/RFOs across the different categories of staff: research, academia, management, and administration. We are referring to individuals who had more active role in the implementation. Detailed list of staff categories participating in each action collected from the partners via *Data collection tool for monitoring and evaluation* and *Integration tool* is available in the *Annex B*. Here we give a brief overview.

Actions implemented by the partners regularly involved different categories of staff. Data show that the following categories were involved:

- research: young researchers (no PhD), researchers (with PhD, not permanent), project managers;
- academia: students, professors, equality and diversity body members;
- management: rector, vice rector, dean, vice dean, head of department, head of office;
- administration: secretary's office, public relations / communications office, research / project support office, rectorate, human resources office, legal office, diversity and equality office, student services office, technical support, educational support office.

The following matrix gives a general overview of participation of different categories of staff in different areas of interventions, not counting the actions or actors. The data reported by the RPOs/RFOs shows broad participation of staff of different categories, and vertical and horizontal collaboration between staff.

Table 3 Overall participation of staff across categories

	Human resources	Institutional governance	Institutional communication	Students services	Research / research funding	Teaching	Transfer to market	Sexual harassment	Intersectionality	Collaborative actions
CALIPER working group	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Research positions										
Young researchers (no PhD)	x	x	x	x	x	x			x	x
Researchers (with PhD, not permanent)	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Project managers	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x
Academic positions										
Students	x	x	x	x	x	x			x	x
Professors	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Equality and diversity body	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x
Management										
Rector		x		x				x		x
Vice rector		x			x					
Dean	x	x	x	x	x	x				
Vice dean	x	x	x		x	x			x	x
Head of department	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Head of office	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	x
Administration										
Secretary office	x	x	x		x	x			x	x
Public relations / communications office	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Research / project support office	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	x
Human resources office	x	x	x	x			x	x		
Legal office	x	x	x		x			x		
Diversity and equality body	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		
Student services office		x			x					x
Technical support	x	x	x		x		x		x	x
Educational support office						x				
Library		x			x					

The overview of actions per RPO/RFO and per different areas of interventions, respectively, is given in the following table. Zooming in the internal engagement at the level of individual partners we note how in most partners (IRB, ECE NTUA, STU BA, UNILE, YU) there was a more even involvement across the different categories while for others the engagement of managerial, administrative, or academic staff was prevailing. Detailed list of staff categories participating in each action is available in the *Annex B*.

Table 4 Participation of staff per RPO/RFO

Partner	Number of actions in which research staff participated	Number of actions in which academic staff participated	Number of actions in which managerial staff participated	Number of actions in which administrative staff participated
IRB	4	5	6	6
ECE NTUA	7	7	7	7
SRNSFG	7	6	12	18
STU BA	4	5	4	5
UEFISCDI	6			
ULB	15	16	8	11
UNILE	2	5	2	2
UZG	3	6	6	3
YU	2	3	4	3

Table 5 Participation of staff per area of intervention

Area of Intervention	Number of actions in which research staff participated	Number of actions in which academic staff participated	Number of actions in which managerial staff participated	Number of actions in which administrative staff participated
Human resources	5	6	6	5
Institutional governance	6	9	11	9
Institutional communication	5	7	7	9
Student's services	5	5	3	3
Research / Research funding	8	6	7	8
Teaching	4	6	3	4
Transfer to market	2	2	1	2
Sexual harassment	2	2	2	4
Intersectionality	1	1	1	2
Collaborative actions	6	9	6	3

3.5 Timeline of the implementation

This section provides details about the timeline of implemented actions. The first iteration of implementation of GEPs covers the period of 12 months, between M18 and M30 (April 2021 – June 2022).

In total, RPOs/RFOs finalized or partially implemented 90 actions, out of which 32 (36%) had delay in the implementation. 11 of the delayed actions were finalized in the 1st implementation period, despite the delay. The remaining actions will continue in the 2nd implementation period, some in the original form and some redesigned.

Figure 17 Distribution of actions according to the timeline of implementation

Figure 18 Distribution of delayed actions across soft/structural categories

When analysing the distribution of delayed actions across areas of interventions, almost 45% of the actions fall into three areas:

- institutional governance 16% (5 out of 32),
- sexual harassment 16% (5 out of 32),
- research / research funding 13% (4 out of 32).

Figure 19 Distribution of the delayed actions

It is worth noting that most delayed actions belong to the areas where most of the structural actions tend to concentrate: institutional governance and sexual harassment.

In the area of research / research funding, four actions have been delayed and they will continue with the implementation in the 2nd iteration.

Research/Research Funding Delayed action	Partner	Soft / structural	Short explanation for the delay given by partner
Dissemination of guideline on the inclusion of the sex/gender dimension in (STEM) research	ULB	Soft	Redesign of measure - moving from dissemination of a guideline to the creation of customized guidelines adapted to ULB context.
Gender balance checking mechanism	SRNSFG	Structural	Deviations in outcome indicators are related to deviations in the timeframe of the action.
Providing evaluators/committee members with gender related guidelines	SRNSFG	Soft	Revising final version of the guidelines by the department of Administration and Law took longer than it was expected.
Establishing award for female scientists in Georgia	SRNSFG	Soft	The delay in the process of final evaluation of submitted candidates and revealing the winners.

In the area of sexual harassment, three actions have been finalized with delay, and the remaining two will continue in the 2nd iteration.

Institutional Governance Delayed action	Partner	Soft / structural	Short explanation for the delay given by partner
Advertising of training on discrimination and harassment targeting STEM faculty authorities and departments / services leaders	ULB	Soft	Needs involvement of newly appointed Diversity and Inclusion officer - position was filled beginning of iteration phase 2
Informative kit regarding sexual and moral harassment	UEFISCDI	Soft	Postponed the release of the kit in order to wait for a public report on sexual harassment in academia to be released first

In the area of research / research funding, four actions will continue in the 2nd iteration.

Sexual Harassment Delayed action	Partner	Soft / structural	Short explanation for the delay given by partner
Dissemination of guideline on the inclusion of the sex/gender dimension in (STEM) research	ULB	Soft	Redesign of measure - moving from dissemination of a guideline to the creation of customized guidelines adapted to ULB context.
Gender balance checking mechanism	SRNSFG	Structural	Deviations in outcome indicators are related to deviations in the timeframe of the action.
Providing evaluators/committee members with gender related guidelines	SRNSFG	Soft	Revising final version of the guidelines by the department of Administration and Law took longer than it was expected.

Establishing award for female scientists in Georgia	SRNSFG	Soft	The delay in the process of final evaluation of submitted candidates and revealing the winners.
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For the remaining actions the most common causes for delay reported by RPOs/RFOs in the tool for data integration fall into the following categories: COVID19 related restraints imposed by the legislators in partner countries, long implementation process when involving different staff and offices of the institution, and coordination with the implementation of other GEP actions.

When analysing distribution of delayed actions across RPOs/RFOs the situation varies. Two partners did not experience any delays in the implementation of the actions (UNILE, UZG), while three partners experienced delays in most of the actions (YU in 50% of the implemented actions, ECE NTUA in 71% and ULB in 63%). The remaining partners experienced delays in minority of actions (SRNSFG in 22%, IRB and UEFISCDI in 33%, STU BA in 17%).

Figure 20 Distribution of delayed actions across partners

4 Implemented actions per partner

In this chapter we provide an overview of implemented actions for each RPO/RFO. The report focuses on the area, timeline and stakeholders involved in the actions. The formative evaluation of the results in terms of objectives, output / outcome indicators of the finalized actions, as already mentioned, they are provided in *D4.2 Interim Formative Evaluation Report – phase 1*. Regarding partially implemented actions, here the available data are reported, while the formative evaluation will be completed after the finalization of the actions.

4.1 Institute for Research in Biomedicine (IRB)

In the 1st implementation period IRB implemented 6 actions. Distribution of implemented actions across areas of interventions is the following:

- human resources (1)
- institutional communication (1)
- institutional governance (1)
- sexual harassment (1)
- student services (1)
- transfer to market (1).

One of the actions is structural and 5 are soft. Two of the actions were implemented with collaboration from external stakeholders. IRB did not report partially implemented actions in the data integration tool for WP3. The implementation of all the actions included research, academic, managerial, and administrative staff. More detailed overview of staff involved in the actions is available in *Annex B*.

Area	Action title	Soft / structural	Status	Staff involved	External stakeholders
Human resources	Review, update and disseminate existing recruitment policies and guidelines, assuring that the documentation has a gender sensitive approach	Soft	Finalized	Academic, managerial, administrative	
Institutional communication	Give internal and external visibility to the new Gender Equality Plan.	Soft	Finalized	Research, academic, administrative	Academic and research institutions, public sector, policy makers
Institutional governance	Consolidate and disseminate Group Leader selection protocol.	Structural	Finalized	Academic, managerial, administrative	
Sexual and gender harassment	Review and update protocol on Sexual Harassment.	Soft	Finalized with delay	Research, academic, managerial, administrative	
Student services / Young scientist	Reinforce equality and diversity topics in onboarding sessions.	Soft	Finalized	Research, academic, managerial, administrative	
Transfer to market	Win Event	Soft	Finalized with delay	Research, academic, managerial, administrative	Academic and research institutions, public sector, Industry

4.2 School of Electrical & Computer Engineering - National Technical University of Athens (ECE NTUA)

In the 1st implementation period ECE NTUA implemented 7 actions. Distribution of implemented actions across areas of interventions is the following:

- collaborative actions (2)
- human resources (1)
- institutional communication (1)
- institutional governance (1)
- intersectionality (1)
- teaching (1).

Three of the actions are considered structural, and 4 are soft. Two of the actions were implemented with collaboration from external stakeholders. ECE NTUA did not report partially implemented actions in the data integration tool for WP3. The implementation of all the actions included research, academic, managerial, and administrative staff. More detailed overview of staff involved in the actions is available in *Annex B*.

Area	Action title	Soft / structural	Status	Staff involved	External stakeholders involved
Collaborative action	Engagement of Role models and dissemination activities	Soft	Finalized	Research, academic, managerial, administrative	Academic and research institutions, industry
Collaborative action	WIn Event	Soft	Finalized with delay	Research, academic, managerial, administrative	Academic and research institutions, public sector, Industry, civil society
Human resources	Implementation of a framework for working conditions of researchers in the ECE-NTUA School	Structural	Finalized with delay	Research, academic, managerial, administrative	
Institutional communication	Support the application of the “Guide of using nonsexist language in administrative documents”	Soft	Finalized with delay	Research, academic, managerial, administrative	
Institutional governance	Collection of gender disaggregated data	Structural	Finalized with delay	Research, academic, managerial, administrative	
Intersectionality	Collection of gender disaggregated data	Structural	Finalized with delay	Research, academic, managerial, administrative	
Teaching and student services	Integration of gender related topics in selected courses and lectures	Soft	Finalized	Research, academic, managerial, administrative	

4.3 Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia (SRNSFG)

In the 1st implementation period SRNSFG implemented 22 actions. Distribution of implemented actions across areas of interventions is the following:

- collaborative actions (7)
- human resources (4)
- institutional communication (3)

- institutional governance (2)
- intersectionality (1)
- research / research funding (3)
- sexual harassment (2).

10 of the actions are structural, and 12 are soft. 11 of the actions were implemented with collaboration from external stakeholders. 16 actions have been finalized and evaluated, three of which with some delay. The remaining 6 actions will continue in the 2nd iteration: for three of them this is in accordance with the GEP, while the other three experienced delay. The implementation of all the actions included research, academic, managerial, and administrative staff. More detailed overview of staff involved in the actions is available in *Annex B*.

Area	Action title	Soft / structural	Status	Staff involved	External stakeholders involved
Collaborative actions	To elaborate ToR for Annual Female Scientists Award with academia and universities	Soft		Research, academic, administrative	Academic and research institutions, civil society, feminist NGOs / gender experts
Collaborative actions	Providing evaluators/committee members with specific guidelines on gender stereotypes	Soft		Research, academic	Academic and research institutions, feminist NGOs / gender experts,
Collaborative actions	Collaboration in the process of creating gender dimension in the evaluation criteria for the future grant calls	Soft		Research, academic	Academic and research institutions, feminist NGOs / gender experts,
Collaborative actions	WIN event	Soft	Finalized	Research, academic, managerial, administrative	Academic and research institutions
Collaborative actions	Organize special targeted events, conference, symposia, e.g., in the frame of "Science Fest"	Soft	Finalized	Academic, managerial, administrative	Academic and research institutions, industry
Collaborative actions	To share information related to women for their popularization on SRNSFG webpage and social media	Soft	Finalized	Administrative	Academic and research institutions
Collaborative actions	To develop institutional communication with the aim to harmonize the STEM system	Soft	Finalized	Administrative	Academic and research institutions, industry
Human resources	Training for the staff involved in recruitment process	Soft	Finalized		
Human resources	Informational brochure/guide for recruited staff about gender equality	Structural	Finalized	Managerial, administrative	
Human resources	Development of exit questionnaire for staff	Structural	Finalized	Managerial, administrative	
Human resources	Provision of different training and activities improving professional skills	Soft	Finalized		
Institutional communication	Elaborate a strategy encompassing measures/actions related to the institutional communication enhancement on the matter of gender equality	Structural	Finalized	Managerial, administrative	
Institutional communication	Create a special section on the website revealing successful Georgian women in STEM/research	Soft	Finalized	Managerial, administrative	Academic and research institutions
Institutional communication	To design and implement a strategic communication plan	Structural	Finalized	Managerial, administrative	

Institutional governance	Collecting gender disaggregated data on the organization institutional level	Structural	Finalized	Managerial, administrative	
Institutional governance	Modifying existing job descriptions in the administration unit of SRNSFG, by adding targeted functions towards gender related issues in the organization	Structural	Finalized	Managerial, administrative	
Intersectionality	Establish the reporting system of disaggregated data collection	Structural	Finalized	Administrative	
Research funding	Gender balance checking mechanism	Structural	Delay	Research, academic, managerial, administrative	Academic and research institutions, civil society, Feminist NGOs / gender experts
Research funding	Providing evaluators/committee members with gender related guidelines	Soft	Delay	Research, managerial, administrative	Academic and research institutions, civil society, feminist NGOs / gender experts
Research funding	Establishing award for female scientists in Georgia	Soft	Delay	Research, managerial, administrative	Academic and research institutions, civil society, feminist NGOs / gender experts
Sexual harassment	Adopt a Sexual Harassment Policy and Establish a Mechanism for Reporting	Structural	Finalized with delay	Administrative	
Sexual harassment	Establish a Mechanism for Reporting	Structural	Finalized with delay	Administrative	

4.4 Slovak University of Technology (STU BA)

In the 1st implementation period STU BA implemented 6 actions. Distribution of implemented actions across areas of interventions is the following:

- human resources (1)
- institutional governance (1)
- research / research funding (2)
- teaching (1)
- collaborative action (1).

Two of the actions are structural, and 4 are soft. Three of the actions were implemented with collaboration from external stakeholders from the industry. Two actions have been finalized and evaluated. The remaining 4 action will continue in the 2nd iteration. The implementation of all the actions included research, academic, managerial, and administrative staff. More detailed overview of staff involved in the actions is available in *Annex B*.

It is important to highlight that the action “WIN event” was not reported by STU BA in the monitoring & evaluation report nor in the integration spreadsheet, since it was not indicated in the GEP. The report of the action is in *D5.3 Engagement activities reporting v.1*. However, for the purpose of homogeneity with the other partners, the action has been counted as an implemented action and considered for the analysis, for the available data.

Area	Action title	Soft / structural	Status	Staff involved	External stakeholders involved
Human Resources	Recruitment procedures	Structural		Research, academic,	

				managerial, administrative	
Institutional Governance	Delegates	Structural	Finalized with delay	Research, academic, managerial, administrative	
Research	Integration of gender dimension in final theses	Soft		Research, academic, managerial, administrative	Industry
Research	Integration of gender issues and the gender dimension into research projects (as well as scientific publications)	Soft		Research, academic, managerial, administrative	Industry
Teaching	Integration of gender in the curriculum	Soft		Academic, administrative	
Collaborative action	Win event	Soft	Finalized	N/A	Yes.

4.5 Executive Unit for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding in Romania (UEFISCDI)

In the 1st implementation period UEFISCDI implemented 6 actions. Distribution of implemented actions across areas of interventions is the following:

- collaborative actions (2)
- human resources (1)
- institutional communication (1)
- institutional governance (1)
- sexual harassment (1).

One of the actions is structural, and 5 are soft. Three actions have been finalized and evaluated. The remaining three action will continue in the 2nd iteration, two of which due to delay. The implementation of all the actions included research staff. More detailed overview of staff involved in the actions is available in *Annex B*.

Area	Action title	Soft / structural	Status	Staff involved	External stakeholders involved
Innovation ecosystem	Implementing quotas/targets when inviting speakers at the events	Soft	Finalized	Research	Academic and research institutions, public sector, policy makers, industry, civil society
WIN event	Event held on May 10th 2022 on the topic of gender equality in responsible research and innovation	Soft	Finalized	Research	Academic and research institutions, public sector, policy makers, industry, feminist NGOs / gender experts
Human resources	Recruitment and selection – Development of an Informative kit	Soft	Delay	Research	Academic and research institutions
Institutional communication	Developing an Informative gender sensitive communication kit	Soft	Finalized	Research	Academic and research institutions
Institutional governance	Establishing a Gender Equality Body	Structural		Research	Civil society

Sexual and moral harassment	Informative kit regarding sexual and moral harassment	Soft	Delay	Research	Academic and research institutions, feminist NGOs / gender experts
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4.6 Université Libre de Bruxelles (ULB)

In the 1st implementation period ULB implemented 16 actions. Distribution of implemented actions across areas of interventions is the following:

- human resources (2)
- institutional communication (3)
- institutional governance (3)
- research (2)
- sexual harassment (1)
- student services (3)
- teaching (2).

Six of the actions is structural, and 10 are soft. One action was implemented in collaboration with external stakeholders. Five actions have been finalized and evaluated. The implementation of all the actions included research, academic, managerial, and administrative staff. More detailed overview of staff involved in the actions is available in *Annex B*.

Area	Action title	Soft / structural	Status	Staff involved	External stakeholders involved
Human resources	Toolkit to attract more female candidates to STEM positions	Soft	Delay	Research, academic	
Human resources	Action-oriented study "Feasibility of affirmative actions for academic recruitment"	Soft	Finalized	Research, academic	
Institutional communication	Hands-on training on inclusive communication for STEM webpages administrators	Soft	Delay	Research, academic administrative	
Institutional communication	Review and update of the communication of current STEM website	Soft		Research, academic administrative	
Institutional communication	Dedicated webpage for the gender+ measure of STEM faculties	Structural		Research, academic, administrative	
Institutional governance	Gender+ commission in STEM faculties	Structural	Finalized	Research, academic, managerial	
Institutional governance	Gender indicators within different STEM disciplines	Soft	Delay	Research, academic, administrative	
Institutional governance	Proposal for a gender-balanced participation in Advisory Boards	Structural	Finalized	Academic, managerial, administrative	
Research	Gender target in STEM PhD juries	Structural	Finalized and evaluated (pending approval from one STEM faculty)	Research, academic, managerial, administrative	

Research	Dissemination of guideline on the inclusion of the sex/gender dimension in (STEM) research	Soft	Delay	Research, academic, administrative	
Sexism and harassment	Advertising of training on discrimination and harassment targeting STEM faculty authorities and departments/services leaders	Soft	Delay	Research, academic, administrative	
Students and student's services	Consultation for a new ULB science and technology qualification program to teach at secondary schools	Structural	Delay	Research, academic, managerial	
Students and student's services	Gender technical support to mainstream the gender+ perspective in ULB science outreach activities	Soft	Delay	Research, academic, administrative	
Students and student's services	Joint ULB-g4g FemTech event	Soft	Finalized with delay	Research, academic	Industry
Teaching	Guide on gender-sensitive teaching	Soft	Delay	Research, academic, administrative	
Teaching	Consultation for an explicit integration of sex/gender+ diversity perspective into STEM curriculum competency framework	Structural	Delay	Research, academic, managerial, administrative	

4.7 Salento University (UNILE)

In the 1st implementation period UNILE implemented 7 actions. Distribution of implemented actions across areas of interventions is the following:

- institutional communication (1)
- institutional governance (1)
- research (1)
- sexual harassment (1)
- teaching (1)
- third mission / transfer to market (1)
- collaborative action (1).

Two of the actions are structural, and 5 are soft. Three of the actions were implemented with collaboration from external stakeholders. All 7 actions have been finalized and evaluated. The implementation of all the actions included research, academic, managerial, and administrative staff. More detailed overview of staff involved in the actions is available in *Annex B*.

It is important to highlight that the action *To carry out activities in schools aimed at promoting a gender culture* was not reported by UNILE in the tool for data integration of WP3. However, it was reported and evaluated in the *Monitoring and Evaluation Report*. Therefore, for the purpose of homogeneity with D4.2 *Interim Formative Evaluation Report – phase 1*, the action has been counted as an implemented action and considered for this analysis, for the available data.

Area	Action title	Soft / structural	Status	Staff involved	External stakeholders involved
Institutional Communication	Create and update on the University website a web page dedicated to the activities of the Vice-Rector for Gender Policies with documents, regulations, news on initiatives and actions in progress related to gender policies	Structural	Finalized	Academic	

	(Gender Budget and other relevant studies and analyses)				
Institutional Governance	Create a coordination group and build a dedicated team.	Structural	Finalized	Academic	
Research	Promotion of actions to increase the visibility of doctoral students and young female researchers.	Soft	Finalized	Research, administrative	Academic and research institutions, public sector
Sexual harassment	Publicizing and informing about the rules and the role of the CUG (Comitato Unico di Garanzia CUG – joint guarantee committee) and of the Ombudsperson and access to their services (including information material)	Soft	Finalized	Academic, managerial	
Teaching	Interdisciplinary seminars on gender issues and feasibility study about the introduction of a gender course	Soft	Finalized	Academic	
Third mission	Increasing the visibility of young female researchers - WIN event	Soft	Finalized	Research, academic, administrative	Academic and research institutions, public sector
Collaborative actions	To carry out activities in schools aimed at promoting a gender culture	Soft	Finalized	N/A	N/A

4.8 University of Zagreb Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing (UZG)

In the 1st implementation period UZG implemented 6 actions. Distribution of implemented actions across areas of interventions is the following:

- human resources (1)
- institutional communication (1)
- institutional governance (1)
- research (1)
- student services (1)
- teaching (1).

One of the actions is structural, and 5 are soft. Four of the actions were implemented in collaboration with external stakeholders. All 6 actions have been finalized and evaluated. The implementation of all the actions included research, academic, managerial, and administrative staff. More detailed overview of staff involved in the actions is available in *Annex B*.

Area	Action title	Soft / structural	Status	Staff involved	External stakeholders involved
Human resources	Pilot program for empowerment of female researchers	Soft	Finalized	Research, academic, managerial	Academic and research institutions, industry
Institutional communication	Establishment of a specialized digital communication channel	Soft	Finalized	Academic, managerial, administrative	
Institutional governance	Reporting on the state of gender equality	Structural	Finalized	Academic, managerial, administrative	

Research	Promotion of the principles of gender equality in technology transfer	Soft	Finalized	Academic, managerial, administrative	Academic and research institutions, industry
Student's services	Attracting new students	Soft	Finalized	Research, academic, managerial, administrative	Industry
Teaching	Integration of the gender dimension in teaching	Soft	Finalized	Research, academic, managerial	Academic and research institutions, industry

4.9 YASAR University (YU)

In the 1st implementation period YU implemented 14 actions. Distribution of implemented actions across areas of interventions is the following:

- collaborative actions (3)
- institutional communication (2)
- institutional governance (4)
- research (1)
- sexual harassment (2)
- teaching (2).

Five of the actions are structural, and 9 are soft. Two of the actions were implemented in collaboration with external stakeholders. Six actions have been finalized and evaluated. YU had delays in implementation of 5 actions. The implementation of all the actions included research, academic, managerial, and administrative staff. More detailed overview of staff involved in the actions is available in *Annex B*.

Area	Action title	Soft / structural	Status	Staff involved	External stakeholders involved
Collaborative actions	Collaborative research and projects	Soft		Academic, managerial, administrative	Academic and research institutions, public sector, industry, civil society, feminist NGOs / gender experts
Collaborative actions	Awareness raising and capacity building trainings	Soft	Delay		
Collaborative actions	The WiN Events	Soft	Finalized	Academic, managerial, administrative	Academic and research institutions, industry
Institutional communication	Gender-sensitive institutional communication guidelines	Soft	Delay		
Institutional communication	Gender-sensitive communication trainings	Soft	Delay		
Institutional governance	Gender equality body	Structural	Finalized	Research, managerial	
Institutional governance	Gender-disaggregated data collection	Structural	Finalized	Research, academic, managerial, administrative	
Institutional governance	Awareness-raising activities	Soft	Delay		
Institutional governance	Declaration of will for gender equality in decision making	Soft	Delay		
Research	Integration of gender into institutional strategic plan and institutional funding mechanisms	Structural	Finalized (new refined)		

			action will start)		
Sexual harassment	Creation of an institutional policy document	Structural	Finalized		
Sexual harassment	Gender Based Discrimination, Violence and Sexual Harassment Prevention Unit	Structural	Finalized		
Teaching	Guidelines on the integration of the gender dimension into curricula and teaching	Soft	Delay		
Teaching	Training and pilot implementation	Soft	Delay		

5 Conclusion

This deliverable is the main deliverable of T3.2 *GEPs Implementation in Each RPO/RFO - 1st Iteration* of WP3 *Implementation of GEPs*. The purpose of this report is to give an overview of all implemented GEPs' actions, both partially implemented and finalized, and show the progress of each RPO/RFO in the first iteration, period M18 – M30. This report focuses on the following aspects of implemented actions: overall statistical data on implemented actions, timeline, internal actors, and external stakeholders engaged in the implementation of actions.

This report D3.1 is complementary to the deliverable of WP4 *Monitoring and Evaluation D4.2 Interim Formative Evaluation Report – phase 1* in the sense that it covers all GEP actions both partially implemented and completely finalized by M30 by partners, while D4.2 reports only finalized actions. As already recalled, due to slightly different data collection procedures, the results of this report may differ from D4.2.

The milestone MS7 *End of implementation phase 1* related to the task T3.2 has been achieved.

The 7 RPOs and 2 RFOs implemented in total 90 actions and measures, during the 1st implementation period. Most of the actions, 58 of them (64%), were finalized.

The distribution of the implemented actions per partner is the following: IRB 6 finalized actions, ECE NTUA 7 finalized actions, SRNSFG 16 finalized and 6 partially implemented actions, STU BA 2 finalized and 4 partially implemented actions, UEFISCDI 3 finalized and 3 partially implemented actions, ULB 5 finalized and 11 partially implemented actions, UNILE 7 finalized actions, UZG 6 finalized actions, YU 6 finalized and 8 partially implemented actions.

The distribution of actions per area are the following: collaborative actions (16), institutional governance (15), institutional communication (13), human resources (11), research / research funding (10), teaching (8), sexual harassment (8), student services (5), transfer to market (2) and intersectionality (2).

A larger part of the actions belongs to the soft category (59 actions or 65%), and the remaining to the structural (31 actions or 35%).

Data show that all RPOs/RFOs engaged in collaboration with external stakeholders while implementing GEPs in the 1st implementation phase. The partners collaborated with external stakeholders in the implementation of 35 actions (39%), 9 of which were WIN events.

Data reported by the RPOs/RFOs shows broad involvement of staff of different categories, and vertical and horizontal collaboration between staff, across different categories of staff: research, academia, management, and administration. This data is related to the Key Performance Indicator *Number of different stakeholders involved in the implementation process in each RPO/RFO*, that will be measured at the end of the 2nd iteration.

In total, 36% of implemented actions had delay in the implementation. 11 of the delayed actions were finalized in the 1st implementation period, despite the delay. The most present causes for delay reported by RPOs/RFOs fall into the following categories: sanitary restraints imposed by the legislators in partner countries due to COVID19 pandemic, lengthy implementation process when involving different staff and offices of the institution, and coordination with implementation of other preceding GEP actions.

Annex A: Monitoring GEPs implementation in Teamwork

Continuous monitoring of implementation of actions was performed via a joint shared dynamical Gantt chart in Teamwork, in view of overseeing timely implementation of actions. The progress was regularly updated on the Gantt chart, and this provided a transparent and easy way to oversee the timely implementation of actions. Below are the sample screen shots of Teamwork. It is important to notice that Teamwork also contains information about actions that have been planned for implementation in the 2nd iteration and have not started yet.

Monitoring timelines of implementation of actions

Figure 21 Screen shot of Gantt chart in Teamwork for ECE NTUA

Figure 22 Screen shot of Gantt chart in Teamwork for IRB

Figure 23 Screen shot of Gantt chart in Teamwork for SRNSFG

Figure 24 Screen shot of Gantt chart in Teamwork for STU BA

Figure 25 Screen shot of Gantt chart in Teamwork for UEFISCDI

Figure 26 Screen shot of Gantt chart in Teamwork for ULB

Figure 27 Screen shot of Gantt chart in Teamwork for UNILE

Figure 28 Screen shot of Gantt chart in Teamwork for UZG

Figure 29 Screen shot of Gantt chart in Teamwork for YU

Monitoring actions

Tasks | + Add Task List Assignee or task name Incomplete Tasks Anytime

Task Name	Task List	Tags	Progress
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> (2.1) Pilot program for empowerment of female researchers	GEP UZG	Collaborative action x Human resources x	90%
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> (2.2) Attracting and retaining female researchers	GEP UZG	Human resources x	0%
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> (2.1) Strengthening the availability of existing measures and services for employees	GEP UZG	Human resources x	0%
<input type="checkbox"/> HR Creation of gender-sensitive protocols for recruitment and hiring	GEP STU-BA	Human resources	0%
<input type="checkbox"/> HR Creation of programs for employee reintegration	GEP STU-BA	Human resources	0%
<input type="checkbox"/> 1. Toolkit to attract more female applicants to STEM academic positions	GEP ULB	Human resources	60%
<input type="checkbox"/> 2. Feasibility study 'affirmative actions in academic recruitment'	GEP ULB	Human resources	0%
<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Feasibility study 'correction standard for career breaks'	GEP ULB	Human resources	0%
<input type="checkbox"/> 4. Feasibility study 'extension of post-doctoral contracts'	GEP ULB	Human resources	0%
<input type="checkbox"/> 1. Toolkit to attract more female applicants to STEM academic positions	GEP ULB	Human resources	80%
<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Feasibility study 'correction standard for career breaks'	GEP ULB	Human resources	0%
<input type="checkbox"/> 4. Feasibility study 'extension of post-doctoral contracts'	GEP ULB	Human resources	0%
<input type="checkbox"/> 1. Setting internal targets for the desired percentage of female representation	GEP NTUA	Human resources	60%
<input type="checkbox"/> 2. Establishment of formal procedures to handle incidents of bias and sexist behaviour in the w...	GEP NTUA	Human resources	40%
<input type="checkbox"/> HR2: Conduct a salary audit regarding equal pay	GEP IRB	Human resources	0%
<input type="checkbox"/> HR3: Plan and develop training actions to raise awareness of the importance of work-life balanc...	GEP IRB	Human resources Teaching	0%
<input type="checkbox"/> HR4: Develop a Parental Leave Guide	GEP IRB	Human resources Institutional communication	0%
<input type="checkbox"/> HR5: Develop a Work-Life Balance Guide	GEP IRB	Human resources Institutional communication	0%
<input type="checkbox"/> IG2: Consolidate and disseminate Group Leader Selection Protocol	GEP IRB	Human resources Institutional communication Institutional management	0%
<input type="checkbox"/> IC3: Develop checklist/guidelines for posting and checking material on institutional social media...	GEP IRB	Human resources Institutional communication	0%
<input type="checkbox"/> Collaborative action n. 1: Introduce measures to avoid bias in selection and evaluation processes	GEP IRB	Collaborative action Human resources Institutional communication	0%
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Developing an informative kit with specific instructions regarding ways to tackle gender discrimi...	GEP UEFSCDI	Recruitment and selection x	0%
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Back-to-work training	GEP UEFSCDI	work-life balance x	0%
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Soft skills training	GEP UEFSCDI	work-life balance x	0%
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mentoring for leadership positions	GEP UEFSCDI	Human resources x	0%
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Internal personal development programmes	GEP UEFSCDI	Human resources x	0%
<input type="checkbox"/> HR: Establishment of gender sensitive recruitment procedures	GEP YU	Human resources	0%
<input type="checkbox"/> HR: Revision of the promotion criteria of staff	GEP YU	Human resources	0%
<input type="checkbox"/> HR: Support measures for underrepresented gender at the institutional level	GEP YU	Human resources	0%

Figure 30 Human resources actions

Tasks : + Add Task List 👤 🔍 🕒 Incomplete Tasks 📅 Anytime 🔍 4 ⋮

Task Name	Task List	Tags	Progress	
✓ [3.2] Reporting on the state of gender equality	GEP UZG	Institutional management X	90%	⋮
✓ [5.4] Promotion of the principle of gender equality in technology trans...	GEP UZG	Technology transfer X	90%	⋮
✓ [3.1] Establishment of a body for gender equality	GEP UZG	Institutional management X	0%	⋮
● IG Development of an Extra Action Plan	GEP STU-BA	Institutional Governance	0%	⋮
● IG Delegates	GEP STU-BA	Institutional Governance	80%	⋮
● IG Methodological handbooks	GEP STU-BA	Institutional Governance	0%	⋮
● IG Gender & Diversity Monitoring system	GEP STU-BA	Institutional Governance	0%	⋮
● TM Supporting all academic (with special emphasis on women) emplo...	GEP STU-BA	Transfer to Market	0%	⋮
● 6. Gender indicators	GEP ULB	Institutional management	20%	⋮
● 7. Proposal: gender-balanced advisory boards	GEP ULB	Institutional management	50%	⋮
● 6. Gender indicators	GEP ULB	Institutional management	80%	⋮
● 4. Gender Equality Office	GEP NTUA	Institutional Governance	70%	⋮
● 10. Creation of an Alumni Network	GEP NTUA	Technology transfer	0%	⋮
● IG1: Develop mentoring programmes to promote career progression	GEP IRB	Institutional management Research Teaching	0%	⋮
● IG2: Consolidate and disseminate Group Leader Selection Protocol	GEP IRB	Human resources Institutional communication Institutional management	0%	⋮
● IG3: Prepare an internal regulations to govern the Equality and Diversi...	GEP IRB	Institutional communication Institutional management	0%	⋮
● IC1: Give internal and external visibility to the new Gender Equality Plan	GEP IRB	Institutional communication Institutional management	0%	⋮
● Collaborative action n. 2: Develop a system to monitor the evolution o...	GEP IRB	Collaborative action Technology transfer	0%	⋮
● Collaborative action n. 3: Engaging with the innovation ecosystems: CA...	GEP IRB	Collaborative action Technology transfer	0%	⋮
● IG: Gender-disaggregated data collection	GEP YU	Institutional management	50%	⋮
● IG: Awareness-raising activities	GEP YU	Institutional management	50%	⋮
● IG: Empowerment programme	GEP YU	Institutional management	0%	⋮
● IG: Declaration of will for gender equality in decision making	GEP YU	Institutional management	0%	⋮
● Annual review of Gender Budget	GEP UNILE	Institutional management	10%	⋮

Figure 31 Institutional governance actions

Tasks : + Add Task List Q Assignee or task name 👤 🔍 🔔 Incomplete Tasks 🕒 Anytime 🔔 1 X ⋮

Task Name	Task List	Tags	Progress
☑ [4.1] Establishment of a specialized digital communication channel	GEP UZG	Institutional communication X	90%
☑ [4.2] Gender sensitive language in legal documents	GEP UZG	Institutional communication X	0%
● IC Online and offline activities, workshops, games	GEP STU-BA	Institutional communication	0%
● CA Communication strategy	GEP STU-BA	Collaborative action Institutional communication	0%
● CA Open days, information panels, lectures	GEP STU-BA	Collaborative action Institutional communication Teaching	0%
● CA Discussions on the importance of equal opportunities	GEP STU-BA	Collaborative action Institutional communication	0%
● 16. Hands-on training on inclusive communication	GEP ULB	Institutional communication	20%
● 17. Inclusive websites and social media	GEP ULB	Institutional communication	0%
● 16. Hands-on training on inclusive communication	GEP ULB	Institutional communication	70%
● 17. Inclusive websites and social media	GEP ULB	Institutional communication	50%
● HR4: Develop a Parental Leave Guide	GEP IRB	Human resources Institutional communication	0%
● HR5: Develop a Work-Life Balance Guide	GEP IRB	Human resources Institutional communication	0%
● IG2: Consolidate and disseminate Group Leader Selection Protocol	GEP IRB	Human resources Institutional communication Institutional management	0%
● IG3: Prepare an internal regulations to govern the Equality and Diversi...	GEP IRB	Institutional communication Institutional management	0%
● IC1: Give internal and external visibility to the new Gender Equality Plan	GEP IRB	Institutional communication Institutional management	0%
● IC2: Creation and promotion of a manual/guidelines on inclusive langu...	GEP IRB	Institutional communication Student services	0%
● IC3: Develop checklist/guidelines for posting and checking material on ...	GEP IRB	Human resources Institutional communication	0%
● IC4: Organise and participate in advanced training on inclusive language	GEP IRB	Institutional communication Teaching	0%
● IC5: Promote institutional engagement in equality and diversity topics ...	GEP IRB	Institutional communication	0%
● SGH2: Review and update protocol on Sexual Harassment	GEP IRB	Institutional communication Sexual harrasment Teaching	0%
● I1: Develop awareness campaigns on Intersectionality	GEP IRB	Institutional communication Intersectionality Teaching	0%
● Collaborative action n. 1: Introduce measures to avoid bias in selectio...	GEP IRB	Collaborative action Human resources Institutional communication	0%
● IC: Gender-sensitive institutional communication guidelines	GEP YU	Institutional communication	30%
● IC: Gender-sensitive communication trainings	GEP YU	Institutional communication	50%

Figure 32 Institutional communication actions

Tasks : + Add Task List 👤 👥 🕒 Incomplete Tasks 📅 Anytime 🔍 1 ✕ ⋮

Task Name	Task List	Tags	Progress	⊕
✓ [6.2] Attracting new students	GEP UZG	Collaborative action ✕ Student services ✕	90%	⋮
✓ [6.1] Strengthening the availability of existing services for students	GEP UZG	Student services ✕	0%	⋮
● 13. Consultation for a new science & technology qualification program...	GEP ULB	Student services	0%	⋮
● 14. Gender mainstreaming in ULB science outreach	GEP ULB	Student services	0%	⋮
● 15. WIn event: g4g-ULB day	GEP ULB	Collaborative action Student services	50%	⋮
● 13. Consultation for a new science & technology qualification program...	GEP ULB	Student services	0%	⋮
● 14. Gender mainstreaming in ULB science outreach	GEP ULB	Student services	50%	⋮
● 9.Seminar on gender topics for students	GEP NTUA	Student services	0%	⋮
● IC2: Creation and promotion of a manual/guidelines on inclusive langu...	GEP IRB	Institutional communication Student services	0%	⋮
● YS1: Reinforce equality and diversity topics in onboarding sessions	GEP IRB	Student services	0%	⋮
● YS2: Integrate gender perspective training in transversal PhD program...	GEP IRB	Student services Teaching	0%	⋮
● Alias Career for transgender students	GEP UNILE	Student services	10%	⋮

Figure 33 Student services actions

Tasks | + Add Task List 👤 🔍 Incomplete Tasks Anytime 🔊 ⌵

Task Name	Task List	Tags	Progress
✓ [5.4] Promotion of the principle of gender equality in technology transfer	GEP UZG	Technology transfer x	90%
✓ [5.2] Promotional campaign on gender mainstreaming in research	GEP UZG	Research x	0%
✓ [5.3] Support for researchers after leave	GEP UZG	Research x	0%
✓ Checking the existence of gender equality in research teams at the project registration stage	GEP SRNSF	Research Funding x	0%
✓ Providing evaluators/committee members gender related guidelines	GEP SRNSF	Research Funding x	0%
● R Integration of the gender dimension in final theses (bachelor's degrees, diploma, dissertations)	GEP STU-BA	Research	0%
● R Integration of gender issues and the gender dimension into research projects (as well as scientific ...	GEP STU-BA	Research	0%
● TM Supporting all academic (with special emphasis on women) employees in technology transfer	GEP STU-BA	Transfer to Market	0%
● 8. Dissemination of guideline sex/gender in research	GEP ULB	Research	40%
● 9. Exhibition 'sex/gender in STEM research'	GEP ULB	Research	0%
● 10. Gender target in STEM PhD jurys	GEP ULB	Research	50%
● 8. Dissemination of guideline sex/gender in research	GEP ULB	Research	40%
● 9. Exhibition 'sex/gender in STEM research'	GEP ULB	Research	0%
● 10. Gender target in STEM PhD jurys	GEP ULB	Research	90%
● 7.Set an internal target and add the indicator "Number of thesis/PhD's/research projects with a gen...	GEP NTUA	Research	60%
● 10.Creation of an Alumni Network	GEP NTUA	Technology transfer	0%
● IG1: Develop mentoring programmes to promote career progression	GEP IRB	Institutional management Research Teaching	0%
● R1: Training sessions on the integration of the gender dimension into research	GEP IRB	Research Teaching	0%
● R2: Create and consolidate a protocol for planning and developing internal seminars, ensuring the p...	GEP IRB	Research	0%
● Collaborative action n. 2: Develop a system to monitor the evolution of women in transfer to market	GEP IRB	Collaborative action Technology transfer	0%
● Collaborative action n. 3: Engaging with the innovation ecosystems: CALIPER FemTech Event	GEP IRB	Collaborative action Technology transfer	0%
✓ Analysis of women participation in research projects	GEP UEFSCDI	Research Funding x	0%
✓ Training on gender equality addressed to research projects evaluators	GEP UEFSCDI	Research Funding x	0%
● RES: Integration of gender into institutional strategic plan and institutional funding mechanisms	GEP YU	Research	30%
● RES: Awareness raising actions	GEP YU	Research	0%
● RES: Gender Researchers Group	GEP YU	Research	30%
● Interdisciplinary seminars on gender issues and feasibility study about the introduction of a ge... 📝 1	GEP UNILE	Research Teaching	10%

Figure 34 Research / Research funding actions

Tasks :
+ Add Task List

👤 👥
🕒 Incomplete Tasks
🕒 Anytime
🔍 1 x
⋮

Task Name	Task List	Tags	Progress
✓ [5.1] Gender mainstreaming in teaching	GEP UZG	Collaborative action ✕ Teaching ✕	40%
● T Integration of gender in the curriculum	GEP STU-BA	Teaching	90%
● CA Open days, information panels, lectures	GEP STU-BA	Collaborative action Institutional communication Teaching	0%
● 11. Dissemination of guide on gender-sensitive teaching	GEP ULB	Teaching	50%
● 12. Gender+ perspective into STEM curriculum competency framework	GEP ULB	Teaching	0%
● 11. Dissemination of guide on gender-sensitive teaching	GEP ULB	Teaching	80%
● 12. Gender+ perspective into STEM curriculum competency framework	GEP ULB	Teaching	0%
● 8.Integration of gender-related topics in selected courses and lectures	GEP NTUA	Teaching	50%
● HR3:Plan and develop training actions to raise awareness of the importan...	GEP IRB	Human resources Teaching	0%
● IG1: Develop mentoring programmes to promote career progression	GEP IRB	Institutional management Research Teaching	0%
● IC4: Organise and participate in advanced training on inclusive language	GEP IRB	Institutional communication Teaching	0%
● R1: Training sessions on the integration of the gender dimension into rese...	GEP IRB	Research Teaching	0%
● YS2: Integrate gender perspective training in transversal PhD programme	GEP IRB	Student services Teaching	0%
● SGH1: Develop internal training on Sexual and Gender Harassment	GEP IRB	Sexual harrasment Teaching	0%
● SGH2: Review and update protocol on Sexual Harassment	GEP IRB	Institutional communication Sexual harrasment Teaching	0%
● I1: Develop awareness campaigns on Intersectionality	GEP IRB	Institutional communication Intersectionality Teaching	0%
● I2: Organise an advanced training session on gender and diversity topics f...	GEP IRB	Intersectionality Teaching	0%
● TEACH: Guidelines on the integration of the gender dimension into curricu...	GEP YU	Teaching	30%
● TEACH: Training and pilot implementation	GEP YU	Teaching	50%
● Interdisciplinary seminars on gender issues and feasibility study abo... 1	GEP UNILE	Research Teaching	10%

Figure 35 Teaching actions

Tasks :
+ Add Task List

👤
👥
🕒 Incomplete Tasks
🕒 Anytime
🔍 2 x
⋮

Task Name	Task List	Tags	Progress
✓ [5.4] Promotion of the principle of gender equality in technology transfer	GEP UZG	Technology transfer X	90%
● TM Supporting all academic (with special emphasis on women) employees...	GEP STU-BA	Transfer to Market	0%
● 10.Creation of an Alumni Network	GEP NTUA	Technology transfer	0%
● Collaborative action n. 2: Develop a system to monitor the evolution of wo...	GEP IRB	Collaborative action Technology transfer	0%
● Collaborative action n. 3: Engaging with the innovation ecosystems: CALIP...	GEP IRB	Collaborative action Technology transfer	0%

Figure 36 Transfer to market actions

Tasks : + Add Task List 👤 👥 🕒 Incomplete Tasks 📅 Anytime 🔔 1 ✕ ⋮

Task Name	Task List	Tags	Progress	+
✓ [7.1] Strengthening the system for combating sexual harassment and disc...	GEP UZG	Sexual harassment ✕	0%	⋮
● SH Implementation of the transparent complaints system	GEP STU-BA	Sexual harassment	0%	⋮
● SH Raising awareness	GEP STU-BA	Sexual harassment	0%	⋮
● 19. Dissemination of training on discrimination & harassment	GEP ULB	Sexual harassment	0%	⋮
● 20. Permanent poster campaign	GEP ULB	Sexual harassment	0%	⋮
● 19. Dissemination of training on discrimination & harassment	GEP ULB	Sexual harassment	0%	⋮
● 20. Permanent poster campaign	GEP ULB	Sexual harassment	0%	⋮
● 11. Formal mechanism dealing with cases of sexual harassment and gende...	GEP NTUA	Sexual harassment	40%	⋮
● SGH1: Develop internal training on Sexual and Gender Harassment	GEP IRB	Sexual harassment Teaching	0%	⋮
● SGH2: Review and update protocol on Sexual Harassment	GEP IRB	Institutional communication Sexual harassment Teaching	0%	⋮
✓ Developing an informative kit regarding sexual and moral harassment	GEP UEFS CDI	Sexual harassment ✕	0%	⋮
● Publicising and informing about the rules and the role of the CUG (Comita...	GEP UNILE	Sexual harassment	20%	⋮
● Dissemination of detailed rules on combating sexual harassment ✎ 2	GEP UNILE	Sexual harassment	20%	⋮

Figure 37 Sexual harassment actions

Tasks : + Add Task List 👤 👥 🕒 Incomplete Tasks 📅 Anytime 🔔 1 ✕ ⋮

Task Name	Task List	Tags	Progress	+
● 12. Collection of Gender Equality data on Intersectionality	GEP NTUA	Intersectionality	50%	⋮
● I1: Develop awareness campaigns on Intersectionality	GEP IRB	Institutional communication Intersectionality Teaching	0%	⋮
● I2: Organise an advanced training session on gender and diversity topics f...	GEP IRB	Intersectionality Teaching	0%	⋮

Figure 38 Intersectionality actions

Tasks : + Add Task List 👤 👥 🕒 Incomplete Tasks 🕒 Anytime 🔍 2 x ⋮

Task Name	Task List	Tags	Progress
✓ [2.1] Pilot program for empowerment of female researchers	GEP UZG	Collaborative action X Human resources X	90%
✓ [6.2] Attracting new students	GEP UZG	Collaborative action X Student services X	90%
✓ [5.1] Gender mainstreaming in teaching	GEP UZG	Collaborative action X Teaching X	40%
✓ Providing evaluators/committee members gender related guidelines	GEP SRNSF	Collaborative action X	0%
● CA Communication strategy	GEP STU-BA	Collaborative action Institutional communication	0%
● CA Open days, information panels, lectures	GEP STU-BA	Collaborative action Institutional communication Teaching	0%
● CA Discussions on the importance of equal opportunities	GEP STU-BA	Collaborative action Institutional communication	0%
● 15. Win event: g4g-ULB day	GEP ULB	Collaborative action Student services	50%
● 13.Engagement of Role models and dissemination activities	GEP NTUA	Collaborative action	50%
● 14.Creation of a "Women in STEM" Network	GEP NTUA	Collaborative action	0%
● 15.ECE-NTUA Open Days	GEP NTUA	Collaborative action	20%
● 16.Information Days and Training Workshops on gender issues in STEM	GEP NTUA	Collaborative action	20%
● Collaborative action n. 1: Introduce measures to avoid bias in selection an...	GEP IRB	Collaborative action Human resources Institutional communication	0%
● Collaborative action n. 2: Develop a system to monitor the evolution of wo...	GEP IRB	Collaborative action Technology transfer	0%
● Collaborative action n. 3: Engaging with the innovation ecosystems: CALIP...	GEP IRB	Collaborative action Technology transfer	0%
● CA: Collaborative research and projects	GEP YU	Collaborative action	30%
● CA: Awareness raising and capacity building trainings	GEP YU	Collaborative action	30%
● CA: The WIN Events	GEP YU	Collaborative action	50%

Figure 39 Collaborative actions

Annex B: Detailed internal staff involved in actions

In this section we give an overview of different internal stakeholders/actors involved in the implementation process in RPOs/RFOs across the different categories of staff: research, academia, management, and administration. Detailed list of staff categories involved in each action was collected from the partners via *Data collection tool for monitoring and evaluation* and *Integration tool*.

Table 6 Overview of staff categories involved in the implementation of actions in the area of Human Resources

Institution	Action title	Involved research staff	Involved academic staff	Involved managerial staff	Involved administrative staff
STU BA	Recruitment procedures	Researchers (with PhD, not permanent), Project managers	Equality and diversity body	Dean, Vice dean	Human Resources Office, Legal Office, Diversity and equality body
ECE NTUA	Implementation of a framework for working conditions of researchers in the ECE-NTUA School	Young researchers (no PhD), Researchers (with PhD, not permanent), Project managers	Professors, Equality and diversity body	Vice dean, Head of Department, Head of Office,	Secretary office, Public Relations office, Research Support Office, Technical support Office
IRB	Review, update and disseminate existing recruitment policies and guidelines, assuring that the documentation has a gender sensitive approach		Professors	Head of Department	Research Support Office, Human Resources Office, Legal Office, Diversity and equality body
SRNSFG	Training for the staff involved in recruitment process				
SRNSFG	Informational brochure/guide for recruited staff about gender equality			Head of Department	Legal Office
SRNSFG	Development of exit questionnaire for staff			Head of Department	Legal Office
SRNSFG	Provision of different training and activities improving professional skills				
UEFISCDI	Recruitment and selection – Development of an Informative kit	Project managers			
ULB	Toolkit to attract more female candidates to STEM positions	Young researchers (no PhD)	Students		
ULB	Action-oriented study “Feasibility of affirmative actions for academic recruitment”	Researchers (with PhD, not permanent)	Professors		
UZG	Pilot program for empowerment of female researchers	Young researchers (no PhD)	Professors	Vice dean	

Table 7 Overview of staff categories involved in the implementation of actions in the area of Institutional Governance

Institution	Action title	Involved research staff	Involved academic staff	Involved managerial staff	Involved administrative staff
ECE NTUA	Collection of gender disaggregated data	Young researchers (no PhD), Researchers (with PhD, not permanent), Project managers	Students, Professors, Equality and diversity body	Vice dean, Head of Department, Head of Office	Secretary office, Public Relations office, Technical support Office
IRB	Consolidate and disseminate Group Leader selection protocol.		Professors	Head of Department	Research Support Office, Human Resources Office, Diversity and equality body
SRNSFG	Collecting gender disaggregated data on the organization institutional level			Head of Department	Legal Office
SRNSFG	Modifying existing job descriptions in the administration unit of SRNSFG, by adding targeted functions towards gender related issues in the organization			Head of Department	Legal Office
STU BA	Delegates	Young researchers (no PhD), Researchers (with PhD, not permanent), Project managers	Students, Professors, Equality and diversity body	Dean, Vice dean, Head of Department, Head of Office	Secretary office, Public Relations office, Research Support Office, Human Resources Office, Legal Office, Diversity and equality body, Student Services Office, Technical support Office, Library
UEFISCDI	Establishing a Gender Equality Body	Project managers			
ULB	Gender+ commission in STEM faculties	Young researchers (no PhD)	Professors, Equality and diversity body	Dean	
ULB	Gender indicators within different STEM disciplines	Researchers (with PhD, not permanent)	Students, Professors		Secretary office, Student Services Office
ULB	Proposal for a gender-balanced participation in Advisory Boards		Professors, Equality and diversity body	Vice rector, Dean, Head of Department	Secretary office
UNILE	Create a coordination group and build a dedicated team.		Professors		
UZG	Reporting on the state of gender equality		Professors	Vice dean, Head of Office	Research Support Office, Human Resources Office, Student Services Office, Library
YU	Gender equality body	Young researchers (no PhD)		Rector, Vice rector, Vice dean	
YU	Gender-disaggregated data collection	Young researchers (no PhD)	Professors, Equality and diversity body	Rector, Vice rector, Vice dean, Head of Department, Head of Office	Secretary office, Public Relations office, Research Support Office,

					Human Resources Office, Student Services Office, Library
YU	Awareness-raising activities				
YU	Declaration of will for gender equality in decision making				

Table 8 Overview of staff categories involved in the implementation of actions in the area of Institutional Communication

Institution	Action title	Involved research staff	Involved academic staff	Involved managerial staff	Involved administrative staff
ECE NTUA	Support the application of the “Guide of using nonsexist language in administrative documents”	Young researchers (no PhD), Researchers (with PhD, not permanent), Project managers	Professors, Equality and diversity body	Dean, Vice dean, Head of Office	Secretary office, Public Relations office
IRB	Give internal and external visibility to the new Gender Equality Plan.	Young researchers (no PhD),	Students, Equality and diversity body		Public Relations office, Research Support Office, Human Resources Office, Diversity and equality body
SRNSFG	Elaborate a strategy encompassing measures/actions related to the institutional communication enhancement on the matter of gender equality			Head of Department	Legal Office
SRNSFG	Create a special section on the website revealing successful Georgian women in STEM/research			Head of Department	Legal Office
SRNSFG	To design and implement a strategic communication plan			Head of Department	Legal Office
UEFISCDI	Developing an Informative gender sensitive communication kit	Project managers			
ULB	Hands-on training on inclusive communication for STEM webpages administrators	Researchers (with PhD, not permanent)	Professors		Public Relations office, Legal Office
ULB	Review and update of the communication of current STEM website	Researchers (with PhD, not permanent)	Students, Professors		Public Relations office
ULB	Dedicated webpage for the gender+ measure of STEM faculties	Researchers (with PhD, not permanent)	Professors		Public Relations office
UNILE	Create and update on the University website a web page dedicated to the activities of the Vice-Rector		Professors		

	for Gender Policies with documents, regulations, news on initiatives and actions in progress related to gender policies (Gender Budget and other relevant studies and analyses)				
UZG	Establishment of a specialized digital communication channel		Professors	Vice dean, Head of Office	Public Relations office, Technical support Office
YU	Gender-sensitive institutional communication guidelines				
YU	Gender-sensitive communication trainings				

Table 9 Overview of staff categories involved in the implementation of actions in the area of Student Services

Institution	Action title	Involved research staff	Involved academic staff	Involved managerial staff	Involved administrative staff
IRB	Reinforce equality and diversity topics in onboarding sessions.	Young researchers (no PhD), Project managers,	Students, Professors, Equality and diversity body	Head of Department, Head of Office	Research Support Office, Human Resources Office, Diversity and equality body
UZG	Attracting new students	Young researchers (no PhD),	Professors	Head of Office	Public Relations office
ULB	Consultation for a new ULB science and technology qualification program to teach at secondary schools	Researchers (with PhD, not permanent),	Professors	Rector, Dean,	
ULB	Gender technical support to mainstream the gender+ perspective in ULB science outreach activities	Researchers (with PhD, not permanent),	Professors		Public Relations office
ULB	Joint ULB-g4g FemTech event	Young researchers (no PhD), Researchers (with PhD),	Professors		

Table 10 Overview of staff categories involved in the implementation of actions in the area of Research / Research Funding

Institution	Action title	Involved research staff	Involved academic staff	Involved managerial staff	Involved administrative staff
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STU BA	Integration of gender dimension in final theses	Young researchers (no PhD), Project managers,	Students, Professors, Equality and diversity body	Vice dean, Head of Department, Head of Office	Diversity and equality body, Student Services Office
STU BA	Integration of gender issues and the gender dimension into research projects (as well as scientific publications)	Young researchers (no PhD), Project managers,	Professors, Equality and diversity body	Vice rector, Dean, Vice dean, Head of Department, Head of Office	Diversity and equality body
ULB	Gender target in STEM PhD juries	Researchers (with PhD, not permanent),	Students, Professors	Dean	Student Services Office, Technical support Office
ULB	Dissemination of guideline on the inclusion of the sex/gender dimension in (STEM) research	Researchers (with PhD, not permanent),	Students, Professors		Public Relations office
UNILE	Promotion of actions to increase the visibility of doctoral students and young female researchers.	Young researchers (no PhD),			Secretary office
UZG	Promotion of the principles of gender equality in technology transfer		Professors	Vice dean, Head of Office	Library
YU	Integration of gender into institutional strategic plan and institutional funding mechanisms				
SRNSFG	Gender balance checking mechanism	Young researchers (no PhD), Researchers (with PhD, not permanent), Project managers,	Professors	Head of Office	Public Relations office, Research Support Office
SRNSFG	Providing evaluators/committee members with gender related guidelines	Young researchers (no PhD), Researchers (with PhD, not permanent),		Head of Office	Research Support Office, Legal Office
SRNSFG	Establishing award for female scientists in Georgia	Young researchers (no PhD), Researchers (with PhD, not permanent),		Head of Office	Public Relations office, Research Support Office

Table 11 Overview of staff categories involved in the implementation of actions in the area of Teaching

Institution	Action title	Involved research staff	Involved academic staff	Involved managerial staff	Involved administrative staff
STU BA	Integration of gender in the curriculum		Students, Equality and diversity body		Diversity and equality body
ULB	Guide on gender-sensitive teaching	Researchers (with PhD, not permanent)	Professors		Public Relations office, Educational Support Office

ULB	Consultation for an explicit integration of sex/gender+ diversity perspective into STEM curriculum competency framework	Researchers (with PhD, not permanent)	Professors	Dean, Head of Department	Secretary office
UZG	Integration of the gender dimension in teaching	Young researchers (no PhD)	Professors	Vice dean	
YU	Guidelines on the integration of the gender dimension into curricula and teaching				
YU	Training and pilot implementation				
UNILE	Interdisciplinary seminars on gender issues and feasibility study about the introduction of a gender course		Professors		
ECE NTUA	Integration of gender related topics in selected courses and lectures	Young researchers (no PhD), Researchers (with PhD, not permanent), Project managers	Students, Professors, Equality and diversity body	Vice dean, Head of Department	Secretary office

Table 12 Overview of staff categories involved in the implementation of actions in the area of Transfer to Market

Institution	Action title	Involved research staff	Involved academic staff	Involved managerial staff	Involved administrative staff
UNILE	Increasing the visibility of young female researchers - WIN event	Researchers (with PhD, not permanent)	Professors		Public Relations office
IRB	Win Event	Project managers	Professors, Equality and diversity body	Head of Department, Head of Office	Public Relations office, Research Support Office, Human Resources Office, Diversity and equality body

Table 13 Overview of staff categories involved in the implementation of actions in the area of Sexual Harassment

Institution	Action title	Involved research staff	Involved academic staff	Involved managerial staff	Involved administrative staff
ULB	Advertising of training on discrimination and harassment targeting STEM faculty authorities and departments/services leaders	Researchers (with PhD, not permanent)	Professors		Diversity and equality body
IRB	Review and update protocol on Sexual Harassment.	Researchers (with PhD, not permanent)		Head of Department, Head of Office	Public Relations office, Research Support Office, Human Resources Office, Diversity and equality body
UEFISCDI	Informative kit regarding sexual and moral harassment	Project managers			

SRNSFG	Adopt a Sexual Harassment Policy and Establish a Mechanism for Reporting				Legal Office
SRNSFG	Establish a Mechanism for Reporting				Legal Office
UNILE	Publicizing and informing about the rules and the role of the CUG (Comitato Unico di Garanzia CUG – joint guarantee committee) and of the Ombudsperson and access to their services (including information material).		Professors	Rector	
YU	Creation of an institutional policy document				
YU	Gender Based Discrimination, Violence and Sexual Harassment Prevention Unit				

Table 14 Overview of staff categories involved in the implementation of actions in the area of Intersectionality

Institution	Action title	Involved research staff	Involved academic staff	Involved managerial staff	Involved administrative staff
ECE NTUA	Collection of gender disaggregated data	Young researchers (no PhD), Researchers (with PhD, not permanent), Project managers,	Students, Professors, Equality and diversity body	Vice dean, Head of Department, Head of Office	Secretary office, Public Relations office, Technical support Office
SRNSFG	Establish the reporting system of disaggregated data collection				Public Relations office, Research Support Office

Table 15 Overview of staff categories involved in the implementation of actions in the area of Collaborative Actions

Institution	Action title	Involved research staff	Involved academic staff	Involved managerial staff	Involved administrative staff
ECE NTUA	Engagement of Role models and dissemination activities	Young researchers (no PhD), Researchers (with PhD, not permanent), Project managers,	Students, Professors, Equality and diversity body	Vice dean, Head of Department, Head of Office	Secretary office, Public Relations office, Technical support Office
ECE NTUA	WIn Event	Young researchers (no PhD), Researchers (with PhD, not permanent), Project managers,	Students, Professors, Equality and diversity body,	Vice dean, Head of Department, Head of Office	Secretary office, Public Relations office, Research Support Office, Student Services Office, Technical support Office
SRNSFG	To elaborate ToR for Annual Female Scientists Award with academia and universities	Researchers (with PhD, not permanent),	Professors		Public Relations office
SRNSFG	Providing evaluators/committee members with specific guidelines on gender stereotypes	Researchers (with PhD, not permanent),	Professors		

SRNSFG	Collaboration in the process of creating gender dimension in the evaluation criteria for the future grant calls	Researchers (with PhD, not permanent),	Professors		
SRNSFG	WIN event	Young researchers (no PhD), Researchers (with PhD, not permanent),	Professors	Head of Office	Public Relations office, Research Support Office,
SRNSFG	Organize special targeted events, conference, symposia, e.g. in the frame of "Science Fest"		Professors	Head of Department, Head of Office	Public Relations office, Research Support Office
SRNSFG	To share information related to women for their popularization on SRNSFG webpage and social media				Public Relations office, Research Support Office
SRNSFG	To develop institutional communication with the aim to harmonize the STEM system				Public Relations office, Research Support Office
YU	Collaborative research and projects		Professors, Equality and diversity body	Vice dean, Head of Office	Research Support Office
YU	Awareness raising and capacity building trainings				
YU	The WiN Events		Students, Professors, Equality and diversity body	Rector, Vice dean, Head of Office	Public Relations office, Research Support Office, Technical support Office
UEFISCDI	Implementing quotas/targets when inviting speakers at the events	Project managers			
UEFISCDI	Event held on May 10th 2022 on the topic of gender equality in responsible research and innovation	Project managers			
STU BA	Win event	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
ULB	To carry out activities in schools aimed at promoting a gender culture	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

